

THE INFLUENCE OF MOTIVATION OF TEACHERS ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN ILORIN EAST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA , KWARA STATE

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Abstract: *The study is designed to find out the influence of teachers motivation on academic performance of secondary school students in Ilorin East Local Government Area of Kwara State. The study specifically finds out the relationship between condition of service, regular promotion and regular payment of salary on students academic performance. Three research questions were formulated for the study. 200 respondents were sampled from the study population. Questionnaire was used to collect relevant information (data) for the study. Data collected was analyzed using frequency counts, mean scores and percentages. The results revealed that motivation enhances academic performance of students. Teachers who are highly motivated perform their duty effectively. Also, it was revealed that regular promotions and payment of salaries brings satisfaction that enhances their teaching commitments. The study recommends that adequate and regular payment of salaries should be made available to the teachers. In addition, it is suggest that Teachers promotion should continue to receive prompt attention.*

Introduction

Decades ago, the teaching profession was the ultimate desire of most educated Nigerians. It was well appreciated, admired, respected, and honored by the lot and was viewed as very profitable. The reason was that teachers lived with great dignity and comfort in the community. They were looked upon with admiration by others. They also commanded a lot of influence, enjoyed comfortable accommodation and other benefits (Amakiri, 2016). Today, things have changed. These changes have negatively affected the social position of teachers in the society. In spite of the above observation, teachers' position in the educational system is very unique. A larger percentage of the work force is constituted by teachers. In fact, they are at the forefront of the effort made towards national development. The role played by teachers in the development of our

National goals and objectives cannot be overestimated.

Motivation is a very important psychological concept which helps an individual to consistently strive to achieve an objective. Motivation is an inner drive in an individual to excel in whatever he or she is doing. Motivation has a dual component of intrinsic and extrinsic values. Extrinsic motivation involves the need to strive to achieve an objective. According to Egbe (2014), teacher motivation is what directs or channel teacher behavior and how the behavior is maintained and sustained. It is the additional incentive given to teachers or workers in order to induce them to work hard.

Regular promotion is another variable that talks about the movement of an employee from one rank to the other. It is a positive way employers can reward their employees. It is a variable that can

motivate or de-motivate teachers' desire to stay or leave the job. Promotion comes with job advancement. Job advancement comes with higher wages and higher wages are associated with change in status and prestige, (Ejiogu, 2002). Teachers will have a change in status and prestige if they are promoted and are allowed to enjoy reasonable benefits from this promotion.

Regular payment of teacher salary can be the only incentive that can enhance teachers' productivity. Regular payment of teachers' salaries provides a spur or zeal in the teachers for better performance.

If these variables are attended to, they could improve academic performance in the school system. Denga (2002) observed that an individual who is motivated is more likely to perform better towards his job than an individual who is not motivated. According to Hanson (2010), people look down on teachers and the teaching profession and regard them as the poor. It has also been observed that teachers are not held in high esteem by the society. The profession is regarded as the least in terms of financial reward. Armed with the view, the researcher sought to examine the teachers' motivation on academic performance of secondary school students in Ilorin East Local Government Area of Kwara State.

Statement of the Problem

The goals of education have not yielded much positive results in spite of the huge funding in education by successive governments in Ilorin East local government area of Kwara State. The government invests substantively in education to ensure that teachers are adequately trained and qualified for the profession. But as soon as they complete their training they leave for other jobs, some of them leave after sometime. The rate at which teachers leave the teaching profession is alarming. It has been noticed that teachers leave for partisan politics; they leave for appointments to top government officials, administrative and executive officers in other commercial enterprises like banks, oil industries and other private companies, to mention but a few. Those who do not have the opportunity to leave the job keep nurturing the intention to do so.

Although the number of trained and qualified teachers increases every year, their performance is not encouraging. They do not

commit and dedicate themselves towards the job. Some of them pick up the job as evening time teachers in some private schools instead of using that time to prepare for the next day's lessons. Some involve themselves in petty trading while classes are going on.

The conditions of service in the teaching job, especially in public schools system can never be comparable with what is obtainable in other professions. Workers fringe benefits, working environment, regular payment of salaries, promotions, nature of administration and opportunities for self-enhancement prevalent in other commercial enterprises like banks, oil industries and so on, caused dissatisfaction among teachers. Teachers in public schools do not enjoy reasonable fringe benefits like sick allowances, paid vacations, free medical services and so on. They are subjected to working in environments that are not conducive, such as: overcrowded, dusty and noisy staffrooms, unequipped libraries and laboratories, no functional facilities that can make their duties less burdensome are available to teachers.

Promotions are also not rapid, even when they eventually come they are not accompanied with reasonable benefits. At times no benefits at all are giving to them. Schools management climate are not always conducive for teachers, they are not consulted before decisions concerning them are taken, they are not part of decision making process, and they don't enjoy free and transparent communication between subordinate and superiors. In most cases some schools are managed with autocratic style of leaders. There are no opportunities for teachers to enhance themselves in order to be professionally competent, except for very few that can see themselves through in-service training with their meager income. Government does not fund their trainings. All these and several others have negatively affected the school system and this make teacher to get disenchanted with their jobs.

Purpose of Study

The main purpose of this study is to determine influence of teachers' motivation on students' academic performance in secondary school in Ilorin East Local Government Area of Kwara State. The study specifically attempts to:

1. Examine the relationship between condition of service and students' academic performance.
2. Determine the relationship between regular promotion and students' academic performance.
3. Ascertain the relationship between regular payment of salaries and students' academic performance.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. How does condition of service relate to students' academic performance?
2. How does regular promotion of teacher relate to students' academic performance?
3. How does regular payment of salary relate to students' academic performance?

Literature Review

Concept of Motivation; Motivation can be defined as a complex socially learned pattern of behaviour involving situations, needs, desires, mechanisms and results. It embraces all factors in an employee's development According to Johnson, (2013). Motivation is the mainspring of action in people. The leader who wishes to incite his followers to reach an objective must hold out the promise of reward once the objective is attained. Motives help people to fulfill their wants, drives, and needs). The term motive therefore implies action to satisfy a need. The term need, want, drive, and motive are often used interchangeably by psychologists. Motivation therefore can be defined as willingness to spend energy to achieve a goal or a reward.

According to Amakari (2016), motivation is the process of influencing or stimulating a person to take action that will accomplish desired goals. However, teachers' motivation is a way of empowering teachers in the occupation and involves the perceptions, variables, methods, strategies and activities used by the management for the purpose of providing a climate that is conducive to the satisfaction of the various needs of the employees, so that they may become satisfied, dedicated and effective in performing their task. In education, teachers should be motivated in order to boost their productivity, effectiveness, efficiency and dedication in performing their task, which will

enhance quality assurance, quality education and quality instructional delivery in the educational system.

Conditions of Service and Students' Academic Performance; Teachers all over Nigeria seem to be looked down upon because of poor work environment manifesting in poor conditions of service. The Nigeria secondary school classroom are poorly furnished, some do not even have chairs for pupils; there are no equipment or infrastructure adequate to promote effective teaching and learning. Several teachers have taught for several years without any form of retraining or professional development to update their skills and methods. It is a known fact that the quality of a teacher and his level of commitment affect the standard of his work. The standard of his work determines the quality of the performance of the children that he teaches. If the good standard of education of children must be maintained, teachers' quality must be improved by improving not only his academic and professional competence but also his work environment. Motivation is a major factor for promoting productivity. Improving the work environment of secondary school teachers will improve their productivity and educational quality.

Regular Promotion and Students' Academic Performance; Promotion of an employee involves movement of employee from one rank to the other, from a lower rank to an upper rank within the same field. What employers give to their employees as a reward for hard work and advancement in the job is promotion. Promotion can serve as a motivator or demotivator for employees. It can also promote or hamper the desire of employee to be stable in the job or to leave the job for another one (Murname, 2014). Ozidi (2008) sees promotion as a positive way employers can reward their employees for their efforts and services in the job. The author also observed promotion as a motivator that can boost the employees' morale and makes them work harder than before.

When employees' promotion takes place, they work efficiently and productivity will increase. If promotion does not take place after an employee has worked tirelessly, it dampens his/her spirit, lowers his/her morale and makes him/her feel frustrated (Ozidi, 2008). Most premature resignations in most organizations are caused by an

employee being stagnated (no promotion – being on a particular rank for a very long time). Also in the school system promotion can hamper or promote some teachers desire to stay on the job or to leave. If they are not promoted, productivity will be low; they will feel so discouraged about the job. The urge to leave the job as soon as possible will emerge and this will encourage attrition. But when promotion takes place, teachers will work efficiently to attain the aim of picking up the job. They will work harder to increase productivity and the desire to pull out will not be there

Regular Payment of Salary and Students' Academic Performance; Regular payment of teachers' salary can make teaching profession attractive in the best way of stimulating both the interest of those in it and those who wish to take teaching as their profession (Egbe, 2014). Regular payment of teacher salary can be the only incentive that can enhance teachers' productivity. In the country, it is the tool that can be used to improve teachers' performance. According to Obwanapaul (2018), motivation consist of tangible things such as bonus payment and regular promotion which may of course mean a rise in salary, leading to attainment of personal intangible altitudes such as recognition, prestige, power and so on. Regular payment of teacher salaries provides a spur or zeal in the teachers for better performance.

Motivation is a very important psychological concept which helps an individual to consistently strive to achieve an objective. Motivation is an inner drive in an individual to excel in whatever he or she is doing. Teacher motivation is what energizes teacher behavior, or what directs or channel behavior and how the behavior is maintained and sustained. It is the additional incentive given to teachers or workers in order to induce them to work hard.

The literature reviewed shows that conditions of service significant relate to students' academic performance. The standard of his work determines the quality of the performance of the children that he teaches. If the good standard of education of children must be maintained, they must be good condition of service for teachers. Improving the condition of service of secondary school teachers will improve their productivity and educational quality. Job security of workers in terms of income and employment will enhance

stability of personnel and a long-term commitment.

Regular promotion significantly relates to students' academic performance. Promotion can serve as a motivator or demotivator for employees. It can also promote or hamper the desire of employee to be stable in the job or to leave the job for another one. Promotion is a positive way employer can reward their employees for their efforts and services in the job. It is a motivator that can boost the employees' morale and make them work harder than before.

Regular payment of salary significantly relates to students' academic performance. It can be the best way of stimulating both the interest of those in it and those who wish to take teaching as their profession. Regular payment of teacher salary can be the only incentive that can enhance teachers' productivity.

From the reviews above, the researcher realized that most of the review was dearth (lack) of literature on the topic under study in the environment where this study was conducted. It is therefore apt to say that literature was not available in the study area which justifies the need for the current study. This study has been carried out by other researchers but using private schools or other motivational studies. It is therefore, the desire of the researcher to carry out this study in Ilorin East Local Government Area of Kwara State as to bridge the gap in knowledge in that area.

Methodology

Descriptive research of the survey type was employed in this study. It involves collection of data for the purpose of describing existing situation, because the research collect data from a select sample and use it to made inferences about the impact of teachers' motivation on students' academic performance in Ilorin East Local Government Area of Kwara State.

Population of the study comprises of all secondary school in Ilorin East Local Government Area of Kwara State.

The sample for this study was 200 respondents, comprising of 20 teachers of both males and female selected from 10 secondary schools. Simple random sampling techniques were use to select the schools to be visited. The ten (10) schools were selected using simple sampling

technique includes collecting the samples from the subgroups. The process was used to select 20 teachers in each school of which a number of 200 teachers were selected.

The questionnaire titled “Teachers' Motivation Questionnaire (TMQ) and Students' Academic Performance questionnaire was used to collect relevant information for the study teacher motivation and students' academic performance. Based on Condition of service, Regular promotion, Regular payment of salary and teaching effectiveness by using 4 – point scale; strongly agree = 4, agree = 3, disagree = 2 and strongly

disagree = 1.

Validity of the instrument was subjected to face and content validity. Reliability of the instruments was done by using test retest method to measure its consistency. The reliability coefficient of 0.85 was obtained. The data for the study were collected by the researcher with the help of research assistants. The data collected were analyzed using of frequency counts, mean scores, and percentages.

Data Analysis

Research Question One: How does condition of service relate to students' academic performance?

Table 4: Results showing how condition of service relate to students' academic performance

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	DECISION	
1.	Motivation enhances academic performance of student.	98	102	-	-	3.45	AGREE	
2.	Teacher motivations facilitate teaching and learning.	77	89	16	18	3.13	AGREE	
3.	Motivation of teachers will help improved performance of students in their examination.	86	90	11	13	2.80	AGREE	
4.	Job satisfaction leads to improvement in the teaching and learning process	100	98	2	-	3.49	AGREE	
5.	Motivation of teachers is very important for educational academic performance.	90	84	10	16	3.24	AGREE	
6.	Performance of unmotivated students is always bad.	72	81	25	22	3.02	AGREE	
	GRAND MEAN SCORE	3.19						

The table above shows the results on how condition of service relate to students academic performance. The first item has a mean of 3.45 showing that motivation enhances academic performance of student. Item two of the same table above has a mean response of 3.13 showing that it was agreed that teacher motivation facilitate teaching and learning. Item three has a mean of 2.80 which is

above the rejected mean of 2.4, this shows that the statement therein in accepted. The statement in item four which says job satisfaction leads to improvement in the teaching and learning process is accepted with the mean response of 3.49. also, item five of the same table above says motivation of teacher is very important for educational academic performance has a mean response of 3.24 which

implies that the statement is accepted. Lastly, the last item of the table has a mean response of 3.02 and this implies that the statement is therein is hereby accepted.

Hence, the results above shows that condition of service is largely relate to students academic performance.

Research Question Two: How does regular promotion relate to students' academic performance?

Table 5: Results showing the how regular promotion relate to students' academic performance

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	DECISION
1.	Regular promotion motivates and inspire me to engage my students on extra lessons	106	76	11	7	3.41	AGREE
2.	The promotion given to me is attributed to my zeal for teaching.	70	88	18	24	3.02	AGREE
3.	Staff promotion is effective instrument for motivation	99	75	09	17	3.28	AGREE
4.	Regular promotion brings satisfaction that can enhance commitment.	89	66	27	18	3.12	AGREE
5.	Development of criteria for regular promotion of teachers will raise their professional status and motivate teachers on their jobs	72	69	36	23	2.95	AGREE
GRAND MEAN SCORE		2.63					

The result of the table above is to find out how regular promotion relate to students academic performance. However, it was find out that majority of the teachers agreed that regular promotion motivates and inspire them to engage their student on extra lesson with a mean response of 3.41. Also, majority of teachers agreed that the promotion given to them is attributed to their zeal for teaching. Based on the statement in item 3 which says staff promotion is effective instrument for motivation, this statement has a mean response of 3.28 which mean the statement is accepted. Item four of the same table which says regular

promotion brings satisfaction that can enhance commitment, majority of the teachers also agreed to this. Lastly, the last item of the same table above has a mean response of 2.95, this implies that the statement in the item is hereby agreed upon.

Therefore, the results of the table above clearly show that there is a strong relationship between regular promotion and students' academic performance.

Research Question Three: How does regular payment of salary relate to students' academic performance?

Table 6: Results showing the how regular payment of salary relate to students' academic performance

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	DECISION
1.	Regular payment of salary will make teachers motivated which makes them to put all their effort to their work and improve student academic performance	85	91	11	13	3.24	AGREE
2.	Other financial benefits (rather than salary) being given to teachers have positive role in their job performance and students academic performance	102	85	06	07	3.41	AGREE
3.	Being on the same salary scale for long (5 and above years) negatively affect your performance on the job	74	79	27	20	3.04	AGREE
4.	<i>Poor salary makes teachers to be lazy.</i>	80	69	35	16	3.07	AGREE
5.	<i>Well compensated teachers are likely to work harder.</i>	87	73	27	13	3.17	AGREE
6.	<i>Regular payment of teacher salary determines their attitude to work.</i>	93	71	22	14	3.23	Accepted
	GRAND MEAN SCORE	2.67					

Table 6 shows the response of teacher on how regular payment of salary related to students' academic performance. Based on the results of the table above it is clearly shown that regular payment has a strongly relationship to students academic performance. The mean responses of each items is above 2.4 which is the rejected mean response. Hence, regular payment of salary is related to students' academic performance.

Discussion

This research work correlates the influence of teacher motivation on the academic performance of secondary school students in Ilorin East Local Government Area of Kwara State. The results shows that motivation enhances academic performance of students, teacher motivations facilitate teaching and learning, motivation of teachers will help improved performance of students in their examination, job satisfaction leads to improvement in the teaching and learning process, motivation of teacher is very important for

educational academic performance and students who are not motivated always perform badly in their academic performance.

The results show that regular promotion of teachers is related to student academic performance. The teachers agree that regular promotion brings satisfaction that can enhance their teaching commitment and development of criteria for regular promotion of teachers will raise their professional status and motivate teachers on their jobs.

The result shows that regular payment of salaries related to students' academic performance. Teachers need to be well paid; they need to be promoted as at when due, their welfare has to be taken care of. A teacher who is happy will definitely be ready to impart knowledge to the pupils while a teacher who is not happy will do otherwise. A motivated teacher strives to put effort together in the classroom so as to affect the students positively. Thus, teacher motivation is a push, a propellant or a force that activates a teacher to teach. This implies

that when a teacher is highly motivated especially in monetary aspect, it affects the students positively.

Conclusion

It is important that motivational packages, facilities are needed for the positive performance of student's in Ilorin East Local Government Area of Kwara State as well as across the entire country. Areas like salaries/wages and promotions need to be looked at. Transformation in these areas will make the teacher teach with commitment, demonstrate high morale, productivity and a high sense of professional vista. On the contrary, if these areas are not transformed, education will witness a bleak feature and society will suffer for it.

Recommendations

Consequent upon the findings above, the following are recommended:

Teacher's salary package should be reviewed upwards with prompt payment and made comparable to that of other professionals.

Adequate and regular salaries and other fringe benefits should be paid. This is because teachers patronize the same markets with other workers. There is the need for teachers to enjoy the same salaries as other professionals.

Teachers' promotion should continue to receive prompt attention. The need for teachers to enjoy the same promotion prospects like other professionals cannot be over emphasized.

Teachers in the rural areas should be given special compensation in form of allowances and other fringe benefits in order to checkmate the concentration of teachers.

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